

Supplementary Material for the paper

“An audio-tactile interface based on dielectric elastomer actuators”

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User interface design

Besides the DE element itself, a core component of the interface is the biasing mechanism. To provide the DE element with a target off-plane pre-stretch and to increase the axial stroke of the end effector upon voltage activation, a suitable biasing element shall be selected, based on the stiffness of the DE element.

The preload and biasing element can be realised in different manners (see Figure S1). To minimize the encumbrance, the weight and the complexity, an inclined negative-rate bias spring (NBS) is used, whose force-stroke response features a region with negative stiffness. This consists in a buckled beam, whose ends are connected to a rigid frame with a certain degree of radial precompression and a certain mounting angle.

Coupling the DE with a NBS allows increasing the available stroke (achieved with a same voltage difference) compared to a design in which the DE is solely pre-loaded off-plane with a positive linear spring (figures on the top row in Figure S1). This happens because the negative NBS stiffness adds up to the positive DE/spring stiffness, leading to a decrease in the total system stiffness. Although in principle a combination of a linear spring and a NBS (middle row plots) can be used to pre-load the DE out of plane and lower down its total stiffness, in practice the pre-load can be directly provided by the NBS (bottom row plots), leading to no stroke reduction compared to an equivalent layout with NBS + linear spring. Changing the dimensions of the NBS (thickness, width, number of layers) and the angle of the NBS, the working point of the system can be set.

Figure S1: Bias Elements working principle: linear biasing element (top), negative bias spring + linear spring (middle) and angled negative bias spring (bottom).

To allow selecting/adjusting the working range of the NBS-DE pair, the distance between the DE and the NBS shall be adjustable. This is realised with two 3D printed parts and a regulation screw. In Figure S2, the adjusting mechanism for the distance between the NBS and the DEA is shown.

Figure S2: Adjustment of the distance between the NBS and DE by means of a regulation screw.

Experimental set-up

The setup used to perform the different characterisation tests discussed in Sect. 4 Experimental Results, is shown in Figure S3. The setup comprises three different working areas:

- An area equipped with a load cell and an LCR meter (left side of the figure), used for the static characterisation discussed in Sect. 4.1 and the blocking tests of Fig. 7(right)/Fig. 10.
- An area equipped with a laser displacement sensor (left side of the figure), used for the tests of Fig. 7(left)/Fig. 10.
- An area equipped with a sound absorbing box with the features and dimensions discussed in ref. [19] and a microphone (central part of the picture), used to perform the presented acoustic measurements

All working areas are equipped with dedicated data acquisition units, based on National Instrument board RIOs. For the tests in Sect. 4.1 and 4.2 excitation signals for the high-voltage amplifier were generated with the same hardware used for data acquisition. For the tests in Sect. 4.3 and 4.5, excitation signals were generated with the STM32 microcontroller integrated in the assembled user interface.

Figure S3: Test rig structures for Measurement results in Chapter 4. Force and LCR meter measurements (left), Laser displacement measurements and acoustic measurements in a sound absorbing box.

Analysis of the DEA static response

The multi-layer DEA layout introduced in Fig. 1 in the main paper and implemented in the prototype demonstrator comprises 3 active layers (subject to HV for actuation purposes) and a sensing layer (operated at low voltage). The sensing layer behaves as a passive layer with respect to the actuation task, which provides the system with a certain share of elasticity, while not participating in the electrostatic force generation process. To evaluate the impact of the sensing layer on the stroke, in the following we present an analysis of the stroke-force response of a COP-DEA (with the same features as the presented experimental prototype) in different conditions.

We express the output static equilibrium force F on the DEA end-effector as a function of the out-of-plane displacement z and the applied voltage V by resorting to a lumped-parameter model of COP-DEAs presented in [Moretti et al., Electroactive Polymer Actuators and Devices \(EAPAD\) XXIII, 2021](#). The model relies on the assumption that the DE

layers can be described as hyperelastic incompressible shells, with ideal dielectric response. By resorting to a discretisation of the membrane, the model allows expressing the DEA membrane force as follows:

$$F = \frac{dU_{el}}{dz} - \frac{V^2}{2} \frac{dC}{dz} \quad (1)$$

U_{el} is the total elastic energy of the DE stack (actuation+sensing layers), which is a function of the stack geometry (diameters, thickness) and the material properties: here we assume that the energy density is described by a 3-parameter Mooney-Rivlin hyperelastic model (with the parameters reported in Table S1, fitted on the tensile curves of the DEA shown in [Gratz-Kelly et al, *Adv Funct Mater*, 2022](#) – supplementary materials). C is the capacitance of the active portion of the stack (actuation layers), which depends on the layers geometry and permittivity (see Table S1).

Table S1. Parameters used for the calculations discussed in this chapter

Model assumptions		
Hyperelast. Params (3-param. Mooney-Rivlin)	$c_{1,0}$	230 kPa
	$c_{2,0}$	8 kPa
	$c_{0,1}$	-29 kPa
Permittivity	ϵ	$2.4 \cdot 8.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m
Trapped air volume	Ω_0	30 cm ³

Figure S4. Force-position response (mathematical model) of a DEA stack with no voltage (black lines) and in the presence of 2.5 kV applied voltage (red lines). Two cases are considered: DEA stack with 3 active layers and a passive sensing layer (solid lines), and DEA stack with 3 active layers only (dashed lines).

The force-displacement response at different voltages (0 and 2.5 kV) is shown in Figure S4 for two different COP-DEA embodiments: a COP-DEA with 4 layers (3 actuation layers and a sensing layer, same as the concept discussed in this paper), and a COP-DEA with 3 actuation layers (with no sensing layer). We assume that, in the equilibrium position (with the membrane preloaded against the NBS), $z \cong 5.25$ mm (see Sect. 4.1). In a first approximation and for design purposes, the NBS used in this work can be treated as a constant force source (in the working region of the present device) with small (or even slightly negative) stiffness compared to the DEA (see also [Gratz-Kelly et al, *Adv Funct Mater*, 2022](#) – supplementary materials). Using this assumption, we estimate the stroke of the COP-DEA as the difference of the equilibrium values of z at different voltages, in the presence of a constant bias force (green segments in Figure S4). Consistently with experimental results (see Sect. 4.1), a COP-DEA with 4 layers produces a stroke below 1 mm when 2.5 kV are applied. If no sensing layer were present, the F - z response of the system would feature lower stiffness (dashed lines), leading to a larger stroke (starting from a same out-of-plane initial displacement). The reduction in the free stroke is on the order of 30%. It is worth remarking that this reduction is lower than that due to the presence of the textile layer in the fully-assemble interface (see Fig. 7(left)).

The difference in force at a given value of z (blocking force, represented by the length of the blue segments in the plot) is, in contrast, constant, as it only depends on the trend of the capacitance (which is the same for both embodiments).

The estimated decrease in free displacement caused by the introduction of the sensing layer is considered acceptable for the purpose of the presented user interface application, in which the DEA works against the user finger, close to the blocking condition.

Effect of the DEA housing on the frequency response

Figure S5. (a) COP-DEA assembly without housing (left) suffering from acoustic short-circuit, and installed inside the box (right). (b) Definition of the first structural vibration mode for the COP-DEA, and surface discretization used to formulate the model (Moretti et al., *Mech. Sys Sign. Proc.*, 2022).

The active COP-DEA unit (as shown in Figure S5a-left) is installed in a 3D-printed housing (see Fig. 4 in the paper). In addition to shielding the DEA electrodes' surface from direct contacts with users, such case acts as an acoustic enclosure for the membrane. The internal structure of the housing has the structures shown in Figure S5a-right, i.e., it includes a slot, where the COP-DEA assembly is located, which eliminates (or significantly reduces) the acoustic short circuit between the front and the back faces of the membrane. Thanks to such feature, the volume underneath the DE membrane (highlighted in blue in Figure S5a-right) approximately behaves as a vented enclosure, which is in communication with the atmosphere only through a small-size (mm-scale) gap at the assembly's perimeter. Such enclosure

- Does not affect the low frequency response (e.g., the pumping motion) of the COP-DEA, because of venting
- Works as a bass-reflex at intermediate frequencies, hence preventing acoustic-short circuits between opposite faces of the DE membrane.

As a result of this, the SPL response of the free DEA at low frequencies in the acoustic spectrum (e.g., in the range 500-900 Hz) differs from that of the boxed DE as shown by the plots in Fig. 9 in the paper, with lower-frequency pitches reaching significantly higher levels in the boxed case as a result of bass reflections.

In the frequency ranges where the structural modes are excited, the boxed air volume can be regarded as a closed adiabatic volume, hence contribution additional mechanical stiffness (in addition to the membrane elasticity) to the structural vibrations of the DE membrane. We hereby show that such additional stiffness can be used to explain the shift in the natural frequency of the first peak (i.e., the first structural mode) in the spectra of the boxed DEA in Fig. 9-left.

We hereby make reference to the model of vibrating cone DEA discussed by [Moretti et al., *Mech. Sys Sign. Proc.*, 2022](#), and Moretti & Rizzello, IFAC-PapersOnline 2022. The model relies on a modal representation of the DEA's dynamics (in the absence of the acoustic enclosure), that can be expressed in the following (linearised) form:

$$\mathbf{M}_\alpha \ddot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \mathbf{D}_\alpha \dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \mathbf{K}_\alpha \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \mathbf{d}_\alpha(v, \alpha) \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is a modal coordinate, which allows mapping the position of a set of points on the DE surface via a linear relationship. Denoting $\mathbf{x} = [r_1, z_1, \dots, r_n, z_n]^T$ a vector of radial/axial coordinates of a set of n points on the membrane profile (see Figure S5b), $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ allows expressing the position of the points as follows:

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{Q}_\alpha \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{x}_0 is the equilibrium configuration of the pre-loaded membrane, and \mathbf{Q}_α is a matrix inducing a change of coordinates, whose columns represent mode shape functions that allow parametrising the deformed shape of the membrane. \mathbf{M}_α , \mathbf{D}_α and \mathbf{K}_α are mass, damping and stiffness modal matrices; \mathbf{h}_α is an excitation coefficient, that depends on the applied time-varying voltage $v(t)$ and the membrane deformation kinematics. The detailed calculation of the different dynamic parameters is discussed in the abovementioned reference papers, and it is based on:

- Lumped-parameter models of the electro-hyperelastic response of the DE membrane (used to determine \mathbf{K}_α and \mathbf{d}_α);
- Simplified assumptions on the effects of aeroacoustic loads on the membrane, which enter \mathbf{M}_α , \mathbf{D}_α (in the form of acoustic added mass and radiation damping), that in turn can be calibrated based on experimental data.

For the purpose of the present analysis:

- We focus solely on the DE's first structural vibration mode, i.e., we assume that the membrane undergoes deformations described by a shape function that leads to bubble-like deformations of the lateral surface (with no axial motion of the end effector) similar to those shown in Figure S5b (red profile). We thus describe the membrane deformation through a single parameter (degree of freedom) α , which allows expressing the coordinates of the deformed membrane's point according to Eq. (3) (in this case, \mathbf{Q}_α is a column vector

expressing the deformation function, and its calculation is detailed in Moretti et al., Mech. Sys Sign. Proc., 2022).

- Since we are exclusively interested in evaluating the natural frequency of a particular vibration mode (rather than the forced response), we consider the DE's free dynamics ($\mathbf{d}_\alpha = \mathbf{0}$) and, knowing that the system is significantly underdamped, we neglect damping by setting $\mathbf{D}_\alpha = \mathbf{0}$.
- We assume that the volume of air underneath the membrane is closed and evolves adiabatically, and the membrane faces are thus subject to a pressure difference as a result of the compressions/expansions caused by the DE bubble-like deformation.

With this assumptions, Eq. (2) can be recast as a scalar (single-degree-of-freedom) equation, with an additional contribution due to the relative air pressure in the enclosed air volume:

$$M_\alpha \ddot{\alpha} + K_\alpha \alpha = p \Omega'(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

Where M_α and K_α are scalars, p is the relative pressure of the air in the closed chamber, $\Omega(\alpha)$ is the volume of the chamber, and $\Omega'(\alpha)$ its first derivative. The term on the right-hand side of (4) renders the generalised (Lagrangian) force (projected on coordinate α) due to the air pressure. Pressure p varies with α according to the adiabatic law for ideal gasses:

$$(p + p_0) \Omega(\alpha)^\gamma = p_0 \Omega_0^\gamma, \quad (5)$$

where $p_0 = 1$ bar is the atmospheric pressure, $\gamma = 1.4$ is the adiabatic exponent, and $\Omega_0 = \Omega(0)$ is the volume subtended by the pre-loaded membrane in the equilibrium configuration. Extracting p from (5) and replacing it in (4) leads to the following nonlinear dynamic equation:

$$M_\alpha \ddot{\alpha} + K_\alpha \alpha = p_0 \left[\left(\frac{\Omega_0}{\Omega(\alpha)} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right] \Omega'(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

Replacing the right-hand term of Eq. (6) with its first order expansion around equilibrium ($\alpha = 0$) leads to:

$$M_\alpha \ddot{\alpha} + \left[K_\alpha + \gamma p_0 \frac{(\Omega'(0))^2}{\Omega_0} \right] \alpha = 0 \quad (7)$$

where the expression into square brackets represents the total stiffness of the system, which includes an elastic contribution (K_α) and an contribution due to the air compressibility. The resulting natural frequency for the structural mode described by α is:

$$f_\alpha = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{K_\alpha + \gamma p_0 (\Omega'(0))^2 / \Omega_0}{M_\alpha}} \quad (8)$$

We calculated K_α (and the shape function \mathbf{Q}_α inducing the definition of α) using the procedure described by Moretti et al., Mech. Sys Sign. Proc., 2022, using the hyperelastic parameters described in Table S1, and a bias voltage of 2500 V. Using the plot in Fig. 9(left), we assumed a value of 900 Hz for the natural frequency of the first structural mode of the free DEA (without enclosure), and we used that to compute M_α from Eq. (8), excluding the contribution of the air compressibility (calculating M_α analytically would involve high uncertainty, due to the contribution of the sound radiation added mass). We then calculated the natural frequency for the assembled DEA (with housing) using Eq. (8) (including air's stiffness), assuming a volume on the order of $\Omega_0 = 30 \text{ cm}^3$ for the air volume (based on the device components' drawings). The estimated natural frequency for the assembled COP-DEA is $f_\alpha = 1050$ Hz, i.e. on the order of 130 Hz higher than the natural frequency of the free DEA. This result is consistent with the position of the peaks in the SPL curve for the assembled device (or slightly higher, since the air volume is treated as completely sealed in the calculations, as opposed to the presence of a small aperture along the assembly perimeter in reality). We conclude that the variations in the acoustic frequency response for the assembled device (compared to the free DEA) can be consistently explained in terms of the bass-reflex effect generated by the DEA's housing design, which fully explains also the shift (increase) in natural frequency of the first structural mode (i.e., the cut-in acoustic frequency).

Definition of the working modes

We programmed the DE interface to perform a number of audio-tactile routines in response to different user inputs (number of touches). In addition to the 3 excitation waveforms illustrated in Figure 10 in the paper, we included two

more composite audio-tactile routines. A complete overview of the implemented working modes (1-5) is shown in the attached video.

The 5 working modes are implemented through voltage inputs in the form given by equation 2 in the paper:

$$u(t) = \sqrt{V_0 + V_1 \bar{u}(t) + V_2 \cdot \check{u}(t)},$$

with $V_0 = \frac{U_{max}^2 + U_{min}^2}{2}$, $V_1 = \frac{U_{max}^2 - U_{min}^2}{2}$, $V_2 = 2U_{max}U_a$, $U_a \ll U_{max}$ (9)

The different modes (hereby numbered in the same order as they appear in the movie), have the following features.

For Mode 1 (Figure 1 top), $u(t)$ only includes a LF component $\bar{u}(t)$ ($\check{u}(t) = 0$), with $U_a = 0 V$; $U_{max} = 2100 V$; $U_{min} = 200 V$ and $\bar{u}(t)$ rendering a square pulse varying between -1 and +1 with time-varying frequency between 3 Hz and 90 Hz.

For Mode 2 (Figure 1 middle) a combination of a vibrotactile ($\bar{u}(t)$) and an acoustic ($\check{u}(t)$) signal is applied, which can be described by setting $U_a = 220 V$; $U_{max} = 2500 V$; $U_{min} = 700 V$ in the equation, with $\bar{u}(t)$ representing a square pulse with frequency of 2 Hz (200 ms 1; 300 ms -1). The high frequency component $\check{u}(t)$ is a sinusoidal signal with a frequency of 850 Hz with an amplitude of 1 when the LF component is U_{max} and 0.3 when the LF component is U_{min} .

For Mode 3 a combination of a vibrotactile ($\bar{u}(t)$) and an acoustic ($\check{u}(t)$) signal is applied with a decreasing and increasing amplitude is applied, which can be described with the equation by setting $U_a = 300 V$; $U_{max} = 2300 V$; $U_{min} = 700 V$ and $\bar{u}(t)$ is a square pulse with a frequency of 5 Hz (140 ms 1; 60 ms -1) with an exponentially decreasing and increasing amplitude (with the amplitude increasing from 0 to the maximum value, and vice-versa in 2.5 s). The high frequency component $\check{u}(t)$ is a sinusoidal signal with a frequency of 800 Hz with exponentially decreasing and increasing amplitude.

For Mode 4 a haptic and acoustic signal is provided when the user is pushing the button. The LF signal consists in a sequence of two ramps, with a superposed HF sinusoidal signal with a frequency of 1318.5 Hz (E_6), and a third ramp with a sequence of 3 HF pitches (E_6 ; $C_6^\#$; A_6 , i.e., 1318 Hz, 1108 Hz, 1760 Hz). The amplitude of the HF pitches has exponentially decreasing trend, so as to emulate the sound of an instrument's key.

The fifth mode (Figure 10 bottom) only consists of a HF music track with a bias voltage of 2300 V and a amplitude of 300 V, and $\check{u}(t)$ replicating a jingle composed by a sequence of keys (sinusoidal signals with exponentially decreasing amplitude).

Supplementary video

The supplementary video shows the DE interface during the execution of the sensing task, and the reproduction of the 5 tactile/acoustic modes described above. For each mode, two video insets are shown. A video inset shows the interaction between the user and the device during the execution of the modes. To visualise the vibration in the LF range, a marble is put on top of the end-effector, as shown in the second inset.

Experimental Results

In the following, additional measurement results are shown to provide a better understanding of the system response. Figure S6 shows measurements of the SPL at different angles, with and without housing (i.e., free DEA sample vs DEA installed inside the acoustic housing). It can be clearly seen that the DE has directional acoustic response, with the SPL decreasing as the angle approaches 90°. Similar to that, lower bias voltage and amplitude lead to a reduction in SPL. The higher frequency peaks shift to lower frequencies for higher bias voltage, as a result of a decrease in the mechanical stress to which the membrane is subject.

Figure S6: Further measurements of the user interface.

In Figure S7 measurements of the end effector displacement are shown. The measurements are performed with different signals (bias voltage and amplitude) and for different frequency ranges. Furthermore, measurement results with and without housing are shown. At higher frequencies the end-effector out-of-plane motion falls to zero, as a result of the system dynamics (governed by the inertia of the rigid end-effector). With the housing, the movement in the lower frequency range is around one half the movement without the housing, due to the increased stiffness owing to the textile layer installed over the end-effector.

Figure S7: Displacement of the end effector for different signals with and without housing.

In Figure S8 force measurements for different pre load forces are shown. Also a comparison of the force measurements at different bias voltages is presented. The force is nearly constant over the frequency and increases with higher bias voltage. For the preload force of 0.1 N and 1 N the output force of the DEA is the same, whereas when the DE is further pushed inward (2N preload) the force decreases, for the DEA moves towards a flat singular configuration. It is worth remarking that the increase in output force measured at higher frequency is an artifact due to the measurement setup, and it owes to mechanical resonance of the DEA + load-cell assembly.

Figure S8: Force measurement for different pre load forces and different bias voltage and a comparison (low right side).

User tests

In addition to user tests with the three excitation waveforms discussed in the paper (Fig. 10), we performed tests with the other working modes shown in the movie, and asked users to separately rate the acoustic and tactile stimulation level

for each of those modes, so as to expand the results presented in Fig. 12. A complete overview of users' rated intensity is shown in Figure S9. The evaluation of the intensity of the acoustic output always falls in the high end of the rating spectrum (above 5). Vibrotactile intensity has been reported to be maximum for Mode 1 (as already discussed, due to higher applied frequencies, to which human touch is more sensitive). Weaker tactile perception was recorded in Mode 3, where a decreasing amplitude of the excitation signal was applied (rendering the tactile stimulation clearly perceivable only during certain phases of the routine), and in Mode 4, where tactile stimulation was conveyed with very LF signals. For this reason, for the user tests of Fig. 14, attention was focused on Mode 2.

Figure S9: Test person rating of the tactile and acoustic output intensity for the different modes (Mode 1- Mode 5) shown in the supplementary movie.

User tests of Fig. 14-15 were performed by presenting the users with 8 different combinations of vibrotactile and acoustic feedbacks coming from two distinct user interface units (Fig. 13). In addition to the confusion matrices in the main paper (Fig. 15), Figure S10 reports a detailed overview of the perception results reported by the users for all cases (1-8, as defined in Fig. 14). Green bars in the histograms represent the actual feedback provided by either of the units (e.g. acoustic on left demonstrator no signal on right demonstrator for case 1 - upper right histogram), whereas blue bars represent user's reported answers (for different experiments with different distances between the units). It can be observed that a better perception of the wright signal is possible with a higher distance of the demonstrators. Reducing the distance especially affects the acoustic assignability, as it is more difficult for the user to understand whether sound comes from the left or the right unit. In spite of these natural and expected trends, the results show that the haptic feedback is highly recognisable and highly assignable; acoustic feedbacks are also, in most case, correctly assigned, with misassignments mostly coming from scenarios in which users wrongfully locate the acoustic feedback on the same side from where they receive a haptic stimulation (see, e.g., the histogram on the bottom left corner).

Figure S10. Statistics of user perception tests with two DEA units (left-right), for 8 different combinations of haptic and acoustic feedbacks produced by the two units.

The confusion matrix in Figure 15 is generated from the bar diagrams of Figure S10 by using the classification table shown in Figure S11. The table allows map wrong (or incomplete) answers produced by the users into off-diagonals entries in the confusion matrices. Wrong answers can be caused either by a misassignment of the unit form which a certain feedback is produced (e.g., sound being produced by the left unit reported as being produced by the right unit), or a particular stimulation not being perceived at all by the user (e.g., the haptic stimulation or, more unlikely, the acoustic one). The entries in the table in Figure S11 have the following meaning:

- The first column corresponds to the signal actually applied on a certain unit (on either of the sides);
- The second column reports possible (wrong or partial) answers given by the user (for that side);

- The third column reports confusion matrix entries, {row; column}, generated as a result of that particular combination. Subscripts 'is' and 'os' stand for 'input side' and 'opposite side' respectively (e.g., if the input to which column 1 refers is on the left side, than 'is' means 'left' and 'os' means 'right', and vice versa);
- The 4th column reports conditions under which a certain entry is generated (as a same combination of values on the first and second column can lead to different entries, depending on the scenario). If no condition is specified (-), the corresponding entry is included in the matrix every time that particular input-answer combination occurs.

Note that some incorrect answer combinations lead to multiple entries in the matrix. For example, a DEA (say, the left one) being reported to produce a combined audio-tactile feedback (when, in fact, it was producing only a haptic stimulation, the acoustic one being generated by the right unit) generates two entries: a diagonal term {haptic_l; haptic_l} accounting for the correct location of the haptic stimulation on the left side, and an off-diagonal {aco_r; aco_l} entry.

If a certain acoustic (or haptoacoustic) signal was applied on either unit, incorrect answers always corresponded to a misassignment of the sound source (left-to-right). For example, in Case 2, sound generated by the left device was interpreted as being generated by the right DEA in 9 cases.

assignment for confusion matrix			
actual input	User answer	classification	Condition
non	haptic	{non_is; hap_is}	-
	acoustic	{non_is; aco_is}	no aco_os
		{aco_os; aco_is}	aco_os
	hapto acoustic	{non_is; hap_is}	-
		{non_is; aco_is}	no aco_os
	{aco_os; aco_is}	aco_os	
haptic	non	{hap_is; non_is}	-
	acoustic	{hap_is; non_is} + {non_is; aco_is}	no aco_os
		{hap_is; non_is} + {aco_os; aco_is}	aco_os
		{hap_is; hap_is}	-
	hapto-acoustic	{non_is; aco_is}	no aco_os
		{aco_os; aco_is}	aco_os
acoustic	non	{aco_is; non_is}	no aco_os
		{aco_is; aco_os}	aco_os
	haptic	{aco_is; hap_is}	-
	hapto-acoustic	{aco_is; aco_is}	-
		{non_is; hap_is}	-
	hapto-acoustic	non	{aco_is; non_is}
{aco_is; aco_os}			aco_os
{hap_is; non_is}			-
haptic		{aco_is; non_is}	no aco_os
		{aco_is; aco_os}	aco_os
		{hap_is; hap_is}	-
acoustic		{aco_is; aco_is}	-
		{hap_is; non_is}	-

Figure S11: Classification table used for the construction of confusion matrices in Fig. 15.